

Comparing internet and phone survey mode effects across countries and research contexts

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Abstract

We compare internet and telephone survey responses across 27 European Union nations and two research contexts, one a choice experiment of willingness to pay to avoid power outages, and the other a social acceptance of energy infrastructure question. The various forms of survey mode effects and the challenges of survey mode choice are documented and developed in the context of statistical theory and an application to an economics survey. We find evidence that survey-mode effects vary across nations and research contexts. We interpret our findings to suggest that the degree of measurement bias can vary strongly between research contexts, for example based on the availability of a perceived socially correct response within a given context. Future survey-based research should evaluate the choice of survey mode in a context and region-specific manner.

Keywords: internet survey; social acceptance; social-desirability bias; survey mode; telephone survey; willingness to pay

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1 Introduction

The preferred mode of survey data collection often varies between disciplines and researchers. Popular modes of data collection include face-to-face, mail, telephone, and internet surveys. Survey mode choice is often based on clerical concerns such as budget, accessibility of the target sample and the ease of data collection, as well as the preferences of the researcher. However, this choice may have real consequences for the responses received (Klausch et al., 2015), and ultimately the conclusions of the research (Breunig and McKibbin, 2011), making it critical to better inform the survey mode choices in empirical research. In particular, the chosen survey mode may introduce biases into the study that stem from various behavioral consequences of the survey-respondent ecosystem. Past research in a variety of academic disciplines, contexts, and geographies has checked for these forms of bias between different survey modes by comparing obtained responses and corresponding parameter estimates across modes and even across variants of the same mode (Maslovskaya et al., 2019; Struminskaya et al., 2015). The past research has inconclusive results, as discussed in detail in section 1.2 below.

A major present day use of surveys, in combination with advanced statistical methods, comes from stated preference research within economics, wherein no clear consensus regarding a preferred survey mode exists (Dillman et al., 2014; Johnston et al., 2017). This deficiency endures despite the development of a broad and deep literature on survey methodology spurred

by the insights of the NOAA stated preference panel in 1993 (Arrow et al., 1993). The primary interest here is that stated preference studies investigating survey mode effects in relation to estimated non-market values have mixed and inconsistent findings (Johnston et al., 2017; Ethier et al., 2000; Boyle et al., 2016; Windle and Rolfe, 2011). A recent seminal article on the best practices in survey-based economics research suggests that survey mode effects appear “[...] context specific” and that the mode choice should also be made based on context (Johnston et al., 2017, pg. 340). However, up until now an explicit investigation of the effects of survey mode across contexts is lacking. We fill this need in the survey research by comparing internet and telephone survey responses across 27 European Union (EU) nations and two research contexts that were included in a single survey completed by the same respondents.¹ The research contexts compared here are a choice experiment of willingness to pay (WTP) to avoid power outages, and a social acceptance of energy infrastructure experiment.

We posit that the inconsistent past findings with respect to the effect of survey mode on collected responses corresponds to the variation in the populations considered and the contexts of previous research. The effects of survey mode on response patterns are tested by estimating choice models that allow for country-specific survey mode effects. We find evidence that survey mode effects vary strongly between research contexts within our study and to

¹In this paper we define a research context broadly as the topic and research question(s) under investigation and the tools, both survey and statistical, that are used to investigate the research question(s).

a lesser degree across nations. This suggests that the effect of survey mode is not constant, but can instead vary as the survey mode is applied to different regions and research questions, which can help explain the varying results of past research of survey mode effects. One interpretation of our findings is that the degree of response bias, possibly driven by social desirability bias whereby respondents give answers they perceive as socially appropriate when speaking with an interviewer, may be driving the observed variation of mode effects between research contexts. The takeaway for future survey-based research is to evaluate the choice of survey mode in a context and country (or region)-specific manner and to think critically about the potential causes of response biases in the research context considered.

The paper proceeds by developing a conceptual framework for the different types of biases related to survey modes and their root causes. The varied results and contexts of past literature investigating survey modes is discussed in section 1.2 with the focus put on research related to stated preferences. We then present our survey instrument in section 2 and the analysis methods and results in section 3. The final section discusses the findings and conclusions regarding the effects of survey mode.

1.1 Typology of survey mode effects

Survey mode effects can be broadly categorized into two types: sampling (i.e. representation) biases arising from different groups of people completing the survey based on the mode employed, and measurement (i.e. response) biases,

whereby response patterns change across survey mode even when the survey and question formats are held constant (Lindhjem and Navrud, 2011a).

Sampling biases include the following. *Sample-frame bias* where the population that is used to draw the sample is limited in some way. For example, an internet-based survey can only sample from the population that has internet access. If this group differs systematically from the target population the results can be biased. *Non-response bias* can occur when only a specific, systematically-different sub-sample of the population completes, or does not complete, the survey. A specific type of non-response bias is *avidity bias* where only those with an interest in the subject matter participate in the survey. (Maguire, 2009)

Measurement biases include *social desirability bias*, where respondents provide answers they deem to be socially desirable when an interviewer is on the phone or present with them, and *satisficing*, where respondents shortcut the cognitive process required to answer the survey question and thus can arrive at a response that does not accurately reflect their beliefs or preferences (Krosnick, 1991). Next we formalize the concepts of sampling and measurement biases in the context of sampling theory.

Preliminaries Consider a survey sample $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_i, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n]$ of random variables where each respondent $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ contributes a vector of information \mathbf{x}_i with probability distribution $f(\mathbf{x}_i|\boldsymbol{\theta})$, where $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are true parameters relating to the target population (e.g. preferences for an en-

vironmental good). The sample \mathbf{X} is assumed to be free of sampling and measurement biases. The researcher's goal is to estimate $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ using an estimator $h(\cdot) : \chi \rightarrow \Theta$, which is a real-valued function mapping from the sample space to the parameter space, as shown in figure 1. A specific value vector of the estimator based on a sample realization \mathbf{X} is an estimate denoted as $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$, with $h(\mathbf{X}) = \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$. We assume this estimator is well-behaved with the usual desirable properties of unbiasedness, consistency, and efficiency.

Figure 1: Conceptualization of survey sample realizations (following notation of Spanos (1999))

Sampling bias Imagine a sample space χ with a distinct subspace χ_2 , as in figure 1; if we sample exclusively from χ_2 we obtain sample realization $\mathbf{X}_2 \in \chi_2$, where respondent i 's realization is subject to probability distribu-

tion $f(\mathbf{x}_i|\boldsymbol{\theta}_2)$. For example, χ_2 may represent the subset of the population with internet access, and the data generated by sampling exclusively from the internet population may be subject to different underlying preference parameters if $\boldsymbol{\theta}_2 \neq \boldsymbol{\theta}^2$. The effect of sampling bias on the estimator using the \mathbf{X}_2 sample realization can be expressed as in (1).

$$\text{Bias}(h(\mathbf{X}_2)) = E[\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} | \mathbf{X}_2] - E[\boldsymbol{\theta}] = E[E[h(\mathbf{X}_2)]] - E[\boldsymbol{\theta}] = \boldsymbol{\theta}_2 - \boldsymbol{\theta} \quad (1)$$

Where the third equality in (1) follows from the unbiasedness assumptions of $h(\cdot)$ in estimating the underlying parameters of the data. However, while $h(\mathbf{X}_2)$ gives an unbiased estimate of $\boldsymbol{\theta}_2$, it gives a biased estimate of the true population parameter if $\boldsymbol{\theta}_2 \neq \boldsymbol{\theta}$. This result is derived for concrete families of estimators in Bethlehem (2010).

Measurement bias Now consider a third survey sample denoted $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} = [\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_1, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_2, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_n]$ where for each respondent $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ allow that the data may be subject to measurement bias expressed as $E[\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i] = E[\mathbf{x}_i + \boldsymbol{\nu}_i] = \mathbf{x}_i + \boldsymbol{\nu}_i$, where $\boldsymbol{\nu}_i$ is a random variable; we write this succinctly for all i as $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{X} + \boldsymbol{\nu}^3$. For simplicity we assume that $h(\mathbf{X} + \boldsymbol{\nu}) = h(\mathbf{X}) + h(\boldsymbol{\nu})$, as

²One can always argue that different sub-populations are subject to different underlying parameters. As shown in Bethlehem (2010) and Biemer (2001), sampling proportionally from different sub-populations allows for unbiased estimation of the population parameters. This is also a key idea behind stratified random sampling methods (e.g. Muneer et al., 2017).

³The measurement bias is here formulated as classical measurement error, as in Hyslop and Imbens (2001). Other forms of measurement error from Hyslop and Imbens (2001) could be considered within this framework, but this is beyond the scope of the present

would be the case in the classic linear regression model (Greene, 2012, sec. 8.5.1). Also, all $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i \in \tilde{\mathbf{X}}$ are subject to the probability distribution $f(\mathbf{x}_i|\boldsymbol{\theta})$ based on the true population parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. Thus, the $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$ sample is free from sampling biases. However, Under these assumptions the bias of the estimator when using the $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$ sample realization can be expressed as in (2).

$$\begin{aligned}
Bias\left(h(\tilde{\mathbf{X}})\right) &= E\left[\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \mid \tilde{\mathbf{X}}\right] - E[\boldsymbol{\theta}] = E\left[E\left[h(\tilde{\mathbf{X}})\right]\right] - E[\boldsymbol{\theta}] \\
&= E\left[E\left[h(\mathbf{X} + \boldsymbol{\nu})\right]\right] - E[\boldsymbol{\theta}] = E[h(\mathbf{X})] + E[h(\boldsymbol{\nu})] - E[\boldsymbol{\theta}] \quad (2) \\
&= \boldsymbol{\theta} + E[h(\boldsymbol{\nu})] - \boldsymbol{\theta} = E[h(\boldsymbol{\nu})]
\end{aligned}$$

Outcomes of interest Under the framework described above we are interested in explaining observed outcomes in survey studies that compare parameter estimates across survey modes, as such differences drive the concern over survey-mode choice. From above we have three samples under consideration. A sample \mathbf{X} that is a random sample such that each $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{X}$ is subject to the probability distribution $f(\mathbf{x}_i \mid \boldsymbol{\theta})$ and the data is obtained without measurement bias. A second random sample \mathbf{X}_2 that may be drawn from a systematically different sample of respondents where each $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{X}_2$ is subject to the probability distribution $f(\mathbf{x}_i \mid \boldsymbol{\theta}_2)$. And a third random sample $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$ that may be subject to measurement bias such that $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{X} + \boldsymbol{\nu}$, but is free of sampling bias where each $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i \in \tilde{\mathbf{X}}$ is subject to the probability distribution

work. The classic measurement error assumes that $E[\boldsymbol{\nu}_i \mid \mathbf{x}_i] = 0$, no other distributional assumptions are made for $\boldsymbol{\nu}_i$, but we note that even if $E[\boldsymbol{\nu}_i] = 0$ the $E[h(\boldsymbol{\nu}_i)]$ can be non-zero, as shown in Greene (2012, sec. 8.5.1) for the classic linear regression model.

$f(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i | \boldsymbol{\theta})$.

Two hypotheses of interest to survey mode research are defined below. These can be operationalized by hypothesis testing for the equality of parameter estimates from regression models. Hypothesis 1.1 tests for the presence of sampling biases in the \mathbf{X}_2 sample.

Hypothesis 1.1 $H_0 : E[\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} | \mathbf{X}] - E[\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} | \mathbf{X}_2] = 0 \implies \text{no sampling bias in } \mathbf{X}_2$

In relation to survey mode this is most relevant to a situation where \mathbf{X}_2 is sampled using a web-based survey and the \mathbf{X} sample is obtained via mail or telephone. Survey mode literature generally views web-based surveys as more prone to sampling biases (e.g. Johnston et al., 2017; Lindhjem and Navrud, 2011a,b; Taylor et al., 2009), especially from sample-frame bias, as most internet panels from which survey respondents are drawn from voluntary opt-in panels and omit the subset of the population that does not access or regularly use the internet (Baker et al., 2013).

Hypothesis 1.2 $H_0 : E[\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} | \mathbf{X}] - E[\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} | \tilde{\mathbf{X}}] = 0 \implies \text{no measurement bias in } \tilde{\mathbf{X}}$

To test this hypothesis researchers would need to ensure that both samples are subject to the same underlying distribution, i.e. $f(\mathbf{x}_i | \boldsymbol{\theta})$, and inform the same underlying population parameters. In other words both samples need to be free of sampling bias and be random samples of the same target population. Studies that accomplish this are noted in the section 1.2. Furthermore, one sample would need to minimize the chance of measurement biases in

response patterns. Web-based surveys are at lower risk for social desirability bias than survey modes that use an interviewer, such as telephone and face to face data collections (Lindhjem and Navrud, 2011b; Kreuter et al., 2009; Chang and Krosnick, 2010; Holbrook and Krosnick, 2009; Heerwegh, 2009). Similarly, with respect to satisficing bias, any survey mode can be at risk. Some of the limited literature on the issue suggests that web-based surveys are subject to lower risk (Schwappach and Strasmann, 2006; Borkan, 2010; Chang and Krosnick, 2010), though others find that internet surveys are subject to equal or higher satisficing bias (Heerwegh, 2009; Malhotra and Krosnick, 2007). As such, it is difficult to conclude that any one mode has higher risk of satisficing (Lindhjem and Navrud, 2011b), and more research is needed into the specific mechanisms of satisficing in non-market valuation as in Boxall et al. (2009). In testing Hypothesis 2.1 an internet sample may still be the best candidate to serve as the sample free from measurement bias, as at least the risk of social desirability bias is minimized.

We derive the conceptual form of the observed bias for studies that compare parameter estimates across samples collected via different survey modes in the Propositions below. Proposition 1.1 shows that the estimated parameters across samples (e.g. internet and phone samples) will differ systematically based on the differences in the underlying parameter vectors that define these samples.

Proposition 1.1 $E[\hat{\theta} | \mathbf{X}] - E[\hat{\theta} | \mathbf{X}_2] = E[\theta] - E[\theta_2] = \theta - \theta_2$

Proposition 1.2 shows that the difference in observed estimates based on

samples from two survey modes where one mode is subject to measurement bias is a function of the measurement bias and specifically of how this bias manifests within the estimator function $h(\cdot)$.

Proposition 1.2 $E [\hat{\theta} | \tilde{\mathbf{X}}] - E [\hat{\theta} | \mathbf{X}] = E [h(\tilde{\mathbf{X}})] - E [h(\mathbf{X})] = E [h(\mathbf{X})] + E [h(\boldsymbol{\nu})] - E [h(\mathbf{X})] = \boldsymbol{\theta} - \boldsymbol{\theta} + E [h(\boldsymbol{\nu})] = E [h(\boldsymbol{\nu})]$

Proposition 1.3 shows that under sampling bias in one sample (\mathbf{X}_2), and measurement bias in the other ($\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$), the differences in the parameter estimates is a function of both forms of bias. In general there is no reason to expect that these origins of bias will cancel out, though Biemer (2001) derives a way to isolate the bias origins under specific conditions.

Proposition 1.3 $E [\hat{\theta} | \tilde{\mathbf{X}}] - E [\hat{\theta} | \mathbf{X}_2] = E [h(\tilde{\mathbf{X}})] - E [h(\mathbf{X}_2)] = E [h(\mathbf{X})] + E [h(\boldsymbol{\nu})] - E [h(\mathbf{X}_2)] = \boldsymbol{\theta} - \boldsymbol{\theta}_2 + E [h(\boldsymbol{\nu})]$

The conceptual framework is used to understand and categorize the survey mode results from past literature in the next section and to contextualize the results from the empirical exercise in section 3.

1.2 Survey mode studies in non-market valuation

The past literature that is most closely related to our effort here is that which has investigated the impact of data collection mode on responses to economic stated preference surveys. These studies are summarized in table 1. The specific findings and methods of key studies are discussed in more

detail below. However, most critical is the variety of results obtained with respect to the effect of survey mode on the estimated non-market values. Five of the fifteen studies surveyed show little to no effect from survey mode choice, two show smaller effects that do not substantially impact the non-market valuation and resulting policy recommendations, while six of the fifteen studies find substantial effects, including the more recent studies of Boyle et al. (2016) and Sandorf et al. (2017). Most studies report a bias of the form in Proposition 1.3, since their survey mode samples may be subject to differences in both measurement and sampling biases. However, some studies carefully control for sampling biases and thus are able to test Hypothesis 1.2 and any remaining observed bias is of the form in Proposition 1.2. Studies typically test Hypothesis 1.1 via comparing descriptive statistics across samples and testing for the equality of means for response rate and socio-demographic indicators.

Contradictory findings of survey mode effects began in non-market valuation with Loomis and King (1994) and Whittaker et al. (1998). Loomis and King (1994) found that Californian respondents to the phone survey had lower WTP for wildlife habitat improvements, while Whittaker et al. (1998) found that phone respondents had higher WTP state park fees in Colorado. In an attempt to clear up this contradiction Ethier et al. (2000) carry out a careful comparison of phone and mail survey methods and find no evidence that survey mode effects responses. The authors ensure the same sampling frame between respondents receiving the mail survey and those being sur-

Table 1: Economic stated preference studies comparing survey modes

Paper	Modes Compared	Geography	Context	Result
Loomis and King (1994)	phone, mail	California	wildlife habitat	lower WTP for phone
Whittaker et al. (1998)	phone, mail	Colorado	state park fees	higher WTP for phone
Ethier et al. (2000)	phone, mail	Buffalo, NY	green electricity	no difference
Marta-Pedroso et al. (2007)	web, face to face	Portugal	steppe bird habitat conservation	lower WTP for web
Olsen (2009)	web, mail	Denmark	landscape conservation	small effects
Fleming and Bowden (2009)	web, mail	Australia	valuing access to an island	no effects
Maguire (2009)	phone, mail, face to face	USA	support Nature Conservancy	no effects
Bell et al. (2011)	web, mail, face to face	USA	inland water quality	significant differences across all modes
Nielsen (2011)	web, face to face	Denmark	air pollution	small effects
Windle and Rolfe (2011)	web, mail	Australia	condition of Great Barrier Reef	no effects
Scasny and Alberini (2012)	face to face, web	Czech Republic	premature death from climate change	small effects
Lindhjem and Navrud (2011b)	web, face to face	Norway	biodiversity	no effects
Boyle et al. (2016)	web, mail	Brisbane, Australia	river and floodplains	lower values for web
Sandorf et al. (2017)	face to face, web	Norway	protection of cold water coral	lower values for web
Campbell et al. (2018)	web, mail, mixed	MT, CO, AZ (USA)	biomass energy generation	no sig. differences in WTP estimates

veyed by phone by selecting potential respondents from a pool of customers of a specific utility company in Buffalo, New York and randomly assigning them a survey mode, thus constituting a test of Hypothesis 1.2 within their specific context. Their study is limited to a highly specific population, and does not consider web-based surveys, which may be the most distinct survey mode in terms of its low potential for social desirability bias. Also, we note that Ethier et al.'s study again differs from previous work in the population sampled, and also in context, WTP for green electricity options in this case, which could be driving the difference in results. The European study from Lindhjem and Navrud (2011b) compares face-to-face and internet surveys in the context of WTP for protecting biodiversity in Norway. The authors are able to sample from the same sampling frame to minimize sampling biases, and find no evidence that survey mode is affecting responses.

A recent study by Boyle et al. (2016) also managed to test Hypothesis 1.2 by taking particular care to ensure that the comparison of web and mail-based surveys did not suffer from sampling frame bias by drawing both samples from an internet panel and randomly selecting a group of respondents that would receive a hard copy of the survey via post. In their valuation of implicit attribute prices for aspects of a riparian ecosystem in eastern Australia the survey mode significantly affected attribute prices in most cases, with mail-based respondents attributing higher values to the various attributes tested. The paper concludes by calling attention to the lack of definitive evidence regarding survey mode effects, and the need to consider *why* respondents

may respond differently across modes.

Other studies outside of economics have directly compared telephone and internet survey media (Booth-Kewley et al., 1992; Knapp and Kirk, 2003; Dillman et al., 2009; Beck et al., 2009; Szolnoki and Hoffmann, 2013; Zhang et al., 2017). These studies differ in context and in the populations sampled, and perhaps correspondingly give varied conclusions with respect to the degree and types of survey-mode-induced biases. For instance, Booth-Kewley et al. (1992) in their survey of attitudes, and Knapp and Kirk (2003) in their survey of personal sensitivity find little difference between paper and web-based surveys. Meanwhile, Dillman et al. (2009) and Szolnoki and Hoffmann (2013) find evidence of sampling bias and changing response patterns across these survey media.

Thus, we note that past literature, both inside environmental economics and in the broader survey research community often find conflicting results with respect to the effects of survey mode on survey responses. While many studies have noted this inconsistency in the literature (e.g. Ethier et al., 2000; Maguire, 2009; Zhang et al., 2017), none have investigated its etiology across research contexts. We note that even in economics studies that have carefully controlled for sampling effects across the tested survey modes, one finds significant mode effects (Boyle et al., 2016), while the other two do not (Lindhjem and Navrud, 2011b; Ethier et al., 2000).

We posit that the inconsistent conclusions with regard to survey mode effects are due to survey mode effects varying across sampled populations,

regions, and the contexts of the research. Populations across regions and nations may have differing degrees of susceptibility to non-response, avidity, and social desirability bias, among others, if socio-cultural proclivities for responding to surveys and appealing to those around you vary by nation, and also relating to how the context of the study is generally perceived in the nation. Indeed psychologists and political scientists have noted that the propensity for social desirability bias can vary across nations and cultures in various contexts, however this insight has not yet been applied to survey analyses (Karp and Brockington, 2005; Dunn and Shome, 2009; Kim and Kim, 2016).

2 Survey Methodology

The survey examined herein was conducted for the SESAME (Securing the European Electricity Supply Against Malicious and Accidental Threats) EU-FP7 research project during the second half of 2012 and first quarter of 2013 in all 27 nations that comprised the EU at that time.⁴ The goals of the survey were to understand the public's experience with, and perception of, power outages, quantify their WTP to avoid power outages, and understand their acceptance of new energy infrastructure projects in their area. The survey had two main experiments included, a choice experiment designed to elicit the respondent's WTP to avoid power outages, and an ordinal question

⁴See Gutierrez et al. (2013) for a detailed account of survey methodology and the English version of the full questionnaire.

designed to assess the respondent's acceptance of a new hypothetical power line being sited near their home.

Administration of the survey proceeded in two distinct phases. The first phase consisted of a recruitment and a screening step. Respondents were recruited into the sample through initial telephone or email contact. Contact information was obtained from general panel lists maintained for survey purposes. The lists primarily came from two companies, one for telephone numbers and one for email addresses, and we note that the quality and exact composition of the lists varied across countries. So we must assume that the sample frame differed across survey mode to some extent, based on the necessity of contacting people through different modes of communication. At this stage potential participants were given a screening questionnaire which asked for respondents' socio-demographic information. Based on the answers to this questionnaire respondents were either offered to take the full survey or thanked and dismissed in order to ensure that the final national samples are representative of each nation's population in the dimensions of gender, age, working status, income, nation, and rural residents.⁵

The second phase was the administration of the actual survey. Phone respondents were sent a cover letter and information booklet, provided in their language, which they were asked to find and reference when the sur-

⁵The specific quota targets were: balanced genders with up to 70% male as males are often the heads of households in many countries, 70% urban residents (live in towns of over 10,000 people), 25-30% of respondents in any one of the four age brackets, no more than 20% students/unemployed respondents who are often easier to recruit, and a representative sample from the top and bottom 20% of the income spectrum.

vey administrator made contact via telephone. Internet respondents were sent an email with the cover letter information contained within, and a link to the online version of the survey. Respondents to the web-based survey were incentivized to participate in a small way by the company that maintains the email list. In order to counteract the possibility that this incentive would cause internet respondents to speed through the survey, the online questionnaire required that respondents spend at least 3 minutes reading the important text sections of the survey, including the texts introducing the choice experiment and acceptance question. Furthermore, if a respondent took less than 10 minutes to complete the survey they were not included in the final sample. Even so, survey duration varied between survey mode, with the telephone survey lasting an average of 30 minutes and the online survey lasting an average of 16 minutes. This is unsurprising given that most online respondents can read faster to themselves than an interviewer is able to read aloud.

Table 2 shows the response rates to the survey, broken down by survey mode. Overall, 4.75% of contact attempts resulted in a completed survey with 13% of emails resulting in a completed internet-based survey and only 3.2% of phone calls resulting in a completed phone survey. These response rates are not directly comparable as many incorrect phone numbers were dialed. 40,144 or 27% of the total 147,802 numbers dialed, and to the adherence to quotas which disqualified 27,841 respondents, or 16% of the total contact attempts. Nevertheless, the lower response rates to the phone survey

suggest potentially larger non-response bias in the phone-based sample. The noted differences between the phone and web-based samples in our study suggest that our data reject Hypothesis 1.1, namely that sampling biases are present between survey mode samples.

2.1 The Choice Experiment

The first experiment included in the survey is a non-market valuation exercise with the goal of estimating respondents WTP to avoid power outages. This vein of research is of interest to public entities and electricity grid planners who must make tradeoffs between expensive investments in electricity grid infrastructure and the cost of potential power outages.⁶ The choice experiment asked respondents to imagine a power outage with a specified duration, start and end time, season, and area (residential street or whole country). A visual depiction of one of the eight scenarios shown to respondents is reproduced in figure 2. We use 1 hour, 4 hours, 12 hours and 24 hours as durations for the outage scenarios, generally reflecting the durations found in the literature (Layton and Moeltner, 2004; Carlsson and Martinsson, 2008, 2007; Baarsma and Hop, 2009; Reichl et al., 2013). Since the number of choice tasks is limited to eight due to length and budgetary constraints, we revealed two scenarios of each duration to every respondent, with the scenarios randomized for each respondent and organized under a D-efficient design.

⁶Readers interested in this topic are suggested to see Nooij et al. (2007); Reichl et al. (2013); Leahy and Tol (2011); Praktiknjo et al. (2011); Cohen et al. (2018b) and Cohen et al. (2018a).

Table 2: Response rates by survey mode and country

	Total Contacts	Completed Surveys	Total Response Rate	Internet Contacts	Completed Internet Surveys	Internet Response Rate	Phone Contacts	Completed Phone Surveys	Phone Response Rate
Total	176072	8359	4.75%	28270	3652	12.92%	147802	4707	3.18%
Austria	7445	305	4.10%	834	148	17.75%	6611	157	2.37%
Belgium	5168	276	5.34%	601	90	14.98%	4567	186	4.07%
Bulgaria	5866	306	5.22%	519	126	24.28%	5347	180	3.37%
Cyprus	5481	266	4.85%	288	75	26.04%	5193	191	3.68%
Czech Republic	8577	334	3.89%	1693	166	9.81%	6884	168	2.44%
Denmark	8209	294	3.58%	1067	133	12.46%	7142	161	2.25%
Estonia	3092	299	9.67%	688	121	17.59%	2404	178	7.40%
Finland	9250	306	3.31%	933	138	14.79%	8317	168	2.02%
France	4108	311	7.57%	1108	131	11.82%	3000	180	6.00%
Germany	8330	344	4.13%	989	195	19.72%	7341	149	2.03%
Greece	7462	317	4.25%	1096	131	11.95%	6366	186	2.92%
Hungary	5194	336	6.47%	2056	146	7.10%	3138	190	6.05%
Ireland	6265	310	4.95%	796	140	17.59%	5469	170	3.11%
Italy	5605	308	5.50%	850	135	15.88%	4755	173	3.64%
Latvia	5280	314	5.95%	597	120	20.10%	4683	194	4.14%
Lithuania	5715	313	5.48%	627	132	21.05%	5088	181	3.56%
Luxembourg	10088	303	3.00%	757	140	18.49%	9331	163	1.75%
Malta	5763	278	4.82%	433	65	15.01%	5330	213	4.00%
Netherlands	4289	304	7.09%	860	128	14.88%	3429	176	5.13%
Poland	8750	335	3.83%	2281	156	6.84%	6469	179	2.77%
Portugal	8896	322	3.62%	2005	155	7.73%	6891	167	2.42%
Romania	5316	294	5.53%	682	131	19.21%	4634	163	3.52%
Slovakia	4906	289	5.89%	1122	99	8.82%	3784	190	5.02%
Slovenia	6745	300	4.45%	1075	136	12.65%	5670	164	2.89%
Spain	8448	328	3.88%	1517	169	11.14%	6931	159	2.29%
Sweden	5337	313	5.86%	1182	156	13.20%	4155	157	3.78%
UK	6487	354	5.46%	1614	190	11.77%	4873	164	3.37%

A “completed” survey in this table means the respondent answered all questions. Some respondents were dropped from our estimation sample of 7,659 due to responses of “don’t know” to key questions.

Figure 2: Example of blackout scenario from the English/UK version of the survey

Table 3: Average respondent characteristics by survey mode

Variable	Phone Respondents	Internet Respondents
<i>male</i>	0.47 (0.5)	0.53 (0.5)
<i>age</i>	53.76 (13.29)	39.57 (12.68)
<i>urban</i>	0.26 (0.44)	0.38 (0.49)
<i>college</i>	0.42 (0.49)	0.39 (0.49)
<i>hhsiz</i>	2.67 (1.25)	2.62 (1.23)
<i>children</i>	0.31 (0.46)	0.39 (0.49)
<i>income</i> (1000's EUR)	19.422 (14.802)	15.209 (11.685)

N=7659 ; Differences in means between internet and phone sub-samples are significant at the 5% level for all variables, based on between-group mean-comparison t-tests. Variables defined in table 5.

After seeing a depiction of a power outage scenario respondents were offered the option to pay a specified amount of money in their native currency to avoid experiencing the outage. This is referred to as the “bid price” and varies for each respondent with a total of four possible bid prices per scenario and country. The bid price design is based on a previous, similar WTP study conducted by Reichl et al. (2013) for the nation of Austria, which used the D-optimality criterion with balanced utilities to set the bids (Huber and Zwerina, 1996; Burgess and Street, 2005). Two of the four bids of each scenario used in the Austrian study are adopted here with a correction for the difference in income distribution between Austria and every other nation. The other two bids of each scenario are held constant between countries to enable cross-country comparison. As expected, the proportion of respondents accepting the option to pay is decreasing in bid price for all four scenarios as shown in table 4.⁷

2.2 Social Acceptance Question

The second major experiment included in the survey was a story of a new aboveground power line built in the respondent’s neighborhood, followed by an ordinal question designed to assess the level of acceptance that respondents have to new electricity infrastructure. This line of research addresses the issue of social acceptance, often given the unpopular eponym NIMBY

⁷For a full analysis of this choice experiment and further discussion of the WTP elicitation please see Cohen et al. (2018a) and Cohen et al. (2018b).

(not in my backyard) syndrome, which can hinder de-carbonization of the electricity grid as the development of important pieces of infrastructure is slowed or blocked by local coalitions.⁸ Respondents were presented with a hypothetical scenario where a new transmission power line with pylons was to be built 250 meters from their home. In some scenarios respondents were given one of three ‘treatment’ scripts which espoused a potential benefit from the power line in the preface of the question.

Next, respondents were asked: “How do you think YOU would react to the announcement of this power infrastructure program?” With the ability to choose between four possible reactions: “definitely not accept without opposition” (DNA), “probably not accept without opposition” (PNA), “probably accept without opposition” (PYA), and “definitely accept without opposition” (DYA).⁹

An initial look at the survey responses from the full sample in figure 3 illustrates the challenge of social acceptance across Europe, with high proportions of DNA responses in many EU nations, and heterogeneous response trends between nations, with some countries exhibiting much higher levels of acceptance than others. Overall, 34% of respondents indicated they would definitely not accept the new project without opposition while only 12% said they would definitely accept. Furthermore, as shown by the second panel of

⁸Further reading on this issue can be found in Cohen et al. (2014); Cotton and Devine-Wright (2013); Elliott and Wadley (2012); Soini et al. (2011); Devine-Wright and Batel (2013); Devine-Wright (2013, 2007); Wuestenhagen et al. (2007).

⁹For more details on the structure and results of the social acceptance experiment please see Cohen et al. (2016).

Figure 3: Proportion of opposition responses to acceptance question in full sample

figure 3, for all but 6 of the 27 EU nations the proportion of responses of either definitely not or probably not accept is greater than half.

3 Analysis and Results

The survey effort yielded 7,741 questionnaires where all the necessary questions had been completed without “don’t know” answers, leaving an average of 286 survey respondents per nation. We analyze the survey data separately for each of the two contexts discussed above, namely, WTP to avoid power outages, and social acceptance. The variables pulled from the survey that are used in one or both of these estimations are defined in table 5.

3.1 Willingness to Pay Model

The choice experiment, explained in section 2.1, is designed to elicit each respondent’s WTP to avoid power outages. Each respondent completed eight choice tasks where they could either experience a hypothetical power outage of specified characteristics or pay the offered bid price P_{is} to avoid the outage. Thus, the data is in panel format with eight observations per respondent. We model the data using a probit model that allows for respondent-specific random effects. As is becoming standard in environmental economics, identification of the probit model is achieved by dividing the respondent i ’s indirect utility related to scenario s by the respondent marginal utility of income; resulting in a price coefficient that is fixed at 1 for all respondents with corresponding unit-level variances. This practice is denoted as the “surplus-space” method in contrast to modeling respondents’ choices in “utility-space”, where the scale of the utility is fixed for all respondents (Sonnier et al., 2007; Train and Weeks, 2005). Further motivation and the corresponding derivation of specifying our model in surplus-space are given in Appendix 1.1.

The model of each respondent i ’s surplus indirect utility related to outage scenario s can thus be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 v_{is} &= d_s(\mathbf{x}'_{is}\boldsymbol{\beta}) - P_{is} + d_s(\alpha_i + \epsilon_{is}) \\
 \alpha_i &\sim N(0, \delta_\alpha^2) \quad \epsilon_{is} \sim N(0, \delta_{i,\epsilon}^2)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

where d_s is the duration of outage s in hours, P_{is} is the bid value shown to

respondent i for scenario s , \mathbf{x} are the explanatory variables defined in table 5, α_i is the random effect term for respondent i , and ϵ_{is} is a model error term. We will observe a positive response to the survey question when $v_{is} > 0$ indicating that the respondent increases their utility by paying the bid price rather than experiencing the outage. The error components $(\alpha_i + \epsilon_{is})$ are both assumed to be normally distributed with population variances, δ_α^2 the variance between respondents, and $\delta_{i,\epsilon}^2$ the variance within respondents. Both error terms are scaled by the duration of the outage to account for the fact that longer outages can have a wider range of possible effects. Finally, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the vector of slope coefficients associated with the explanatory variables. The elements of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ are interpreted as the marginal effects of a one unit increase in the associated variable on the WTP to avoid an hour of power outage. The specification of the variances within respondents on unit-level suggests a hierarchical Bayesian approach for the estimation of the model.

We estimate two runs of the model in (3) that vary based on the survey-mode variables included. Both models contain fixed effects¹⁰ at the country level to control for unobserved heterogeneity and a group of respondent-specific and scenario-specific control variables. The included variables are defined in table 5. Since both models are estimated in the Bayesian fashion, the output is a posterior distribution for each parameter. We summarize each posterior distribution by its mean, the probability to the right of zero,

¹⁰Specifically, we specify independent priors over each of the country indicator variables as discussed in e.g. Rossi et al. (2005) and Rendon (2013).

and the 95% credible interval, which here is defined as the highest posterior density (HPD) interval that 95% of the posterior probability lies between.

Using the output from the second model, which contains country-specific indicators for survey mode, we calculate the average WTP to avoid an hour of power outage in each nation; following Campbell (2007) we include the random effects term in this calculation. The mean WTP figures are shown in table 6 for the full sample and for the sub-samples of web-based and phone survey respondents. Mean WTP is shown to be highly heterogeneous across nations and higher for phone respondents than web-based respondents, with an average value across the sample of €0.74, an average value of €0.13 for internet respondents, and an average value of €1.18 for phone respondents.

The first model accounts for survey mode with a simple indicator variable that takes a value of 1 if the respondent used the internet survey medium, we call this variable “*web*”. The estimates of the β parameters from this model are summarized in table 7. The results show that survey medium has a strong effect on response patterns in this context, where web-based surveys decrease the WTP to avoid an hour of power outage by €0.73, on average.

To search for heterogeneity in the effect of survey mode on WTP we estimate a second model which includes interaction terms between the *web* variable and country indicator terms. From this model we can estimate the effect of survey mode on WTP in each nation. The results relating to survey mode from this model are summarized in table 8. We find that web-based survey mode reduces estimated WTP in 26 of the 27 countries

in our sample. While the sign of the estimate is the same across these 26 nations, there is notable heterogeneity in the magnitude of the estimated effects of survey mode across nations. Notably, some nations exhibit mean effects much greater in magnitude than the average effect of -0.73, including Denmark, Finland, Luxembourg, Slovenia, and Cyprus. The lone outlier is France, which shows no effect from survey mode, however this is likely due to the extremely low WTP exhibited by France overall.

Table 4: Proportion of respondents who accepted the offered bid by scenario

	Scenario			
	1	2	3	4
lowest bid	0.65	0.81	0.60	0.55
low bid	0.48	0.68	0.47	0.41
high bid	0.34	0.44	0.25	0.34
highest bid	0.29	0.33	0.20	0.18

N=7,741

Table 5: Descriptions of explanatory variables used in econometric analysis

Variable Name	Description
Respondent-specific variables included in both models	
<i>web</i>	took the web-based survey
<i>urban</i>	lives in urban area
<i>male</i>	is male
<i>age35t45</i>	between age 35 and 45
<i>age46t60</i>	between age 46 and 60
<i>over60</i>	over age 60
<i>hhsiz</i>	number of household members
<i>college</i>	college degree
<i>out1t4</i>	experienced 1-4 hour outage
<i>out4t8</i>	experienced 4-8 hour outage
<i>out8t24</i>	experienced 8-24 hour outage
<i>over24</i>	experienced over 24 hour outage
<i>numoutages</i>	number of outages in past year
Variables relevant only to the WTP choice experiment	
<i>rotation</i>	dummy variable for the ordering of the choice scenarios
<i>summer</i>	scenario specified summer power outage
<i>wholecountry</i>	scenario specified power outage across entire nation
Variables relevant only to the social acceptance experiment	
<i>income</i>	self-reported net income (1000's EUR)
<i>T1</i>	was told new power lines will have economic benefits
<i>T2</i>	was told new power lines will have environmental benefits
<i>T3</i>	was told new power lines will have community benefits
<i>posutil</i>	respondent has positive view of their energy provider
<i>negutil</i>	respondent has negative view of their energy provider
<i>satisfied</i>	respondent is satisfied with their supply security
<i>yearsinhome</i>	number of years respondent has lived at current home
<i>needsgrids</i>	believes grid expansion is necessary

Omitted categories for dummy-coded variables are the following, from top down:

Table 6: Mean WTP to avoid 1 hour of power outage in each EU-27 nation overall and by survey mode (EUR)

Country	Full Sample		Web - based Respondents		Phone Respondents	
	Mean WTP	S.D. of WTP	Mean WTP	S.D. of WTP	Mean WTP	S.D. of WTP
<i>France</i>	-0.242	0.085	-0.199	0.127	-0.274	0.115
<i>Germany</i>	0.704	0.073	0.248	0.096	1.295	0.110
<i>Italy</i>	0.743	0.076	-0.135	0.126	1.390	0.097
<i>UK</i>	0.668	0.065	0.375	0.092	0.950	0.091
<i>Austria</i>	0.701	0.076	0.191	0.106	1.145	0.108
<i>Belgium</i>	0.497	0.082	0.161	0.141	0.659	0.099
<i>Denmark</i>	1.424	0.101	0.355	0.121	2.254	0.148
<i>Finland</i>	1.096	0.077	0.007	0.119	1.907	0.101
<i>Netherlands</i>	0.432	0.076	0.122	0.120	0.647	0.094
<i>Spain</i>	0.680	0.075	0.107	0.095	1.249	0.118
<i>Sweden</i>	0.578	0.072	0.019	0.110	1.088	0.098
<i>Portugal</i>	0.466	0.070	0.000	0.098	0.937	0.097
<i>Ireland</i>	0.944	0.065	0.391	0.098	1.390	0.090
<i>Luxembourg</i>	1.484	0.103	0.157	0.134	2.519	0.153
<i>Bulgaria</i>	0.686	0.081	0.255	0.100	0.988	0.118
<i>Czech Republic</i>	0.104	0.081	-0.588	0.139	0.719	0.091
<i>Estonia</i>	0.481	0.074	-0.386	0.137	1.002	0.082
<i>Hungary</i>	0.788	0.061	0.357	0.088	1.099	0.081
<i>Latvia</i>	0.363	0.065	0.054	0.111	0.529	0.082
<i>Lithuania</i>	0.621	0.060	0.278	0.092	0.854	0.081
<i>Poland</i>	0.962	0.069	0.157	0.099	1.618	0.095
<i>Romania</i>	0.908	0.074	0.624	0.106	1.126	0.105
<i>Slovakia</i>	0.612	0.070	0.046	0.113	0.905	0.091
<i>Slovenia</i>	1.036	0.079	0.086	0.106	1.780	0.110
<i>Greece</i>	0.902	0.071	0.414	0.109	1.237	0.094
<i>Cyprus</i>	1.214	0.097	-0.317	0.210	1.655	0.110
<i>Malta</i>	1.069	0.077	0.600	0.146	1.199	0.087
Average	0.738	0.076	0.125	0.116	1.180	0.102

Mean WTP figures are aggregated across respondents and outage scenarios; S.D. (Standard Deviation) is reported. The 95% credible intervals for avg. web and phone WTP do not overlap, suggesting a significant survey mode effect.

Table 7: Estimation results for respondent-specific variables effect on WTP to avoid an hour of power outage (EUR)

Variable	95% credible interval		MEAN	95% credible interval		P>0
	lower bound			upper bound		
<i>web</i>	-0.79		-0.73	-0.68		0.00
<i>rotation</i>	0.06		0.10	0.15		1.00
<i>urban</i>	0.08		0.13	0.19		1.00
<i>male</i>	-0.13		-0.09	-0.04		0.00
<i>age35t45</i>	-0.04		0.03	0.10		0.81
<i>age46t60</i>	-0.05		0.02	0.09		0.71
<i>over60</i>	-0.01		0.07	0.15		0.96
<i>hhsiz</i>	0.04		0.06	0.08		1.00
<i>college</i>	0.14		0.19	0.23		1.00
<i>out_1t4</i>	-0.01		0.05	0.10		0.95
<i>out_4t8</i>	-0.09		-0.02	0.06		0.33
<i>out_8t24</i>	-0.16		-0.06	0.04		0.11
<i>out_over24</i>	-0.25		-0.13	-0.02		0.01
<i>numoutages</i>	-0.01		0.00	0.00		0.08
<i>summer</i>	-0.82		-0.78	-0.73		0.00
<i>wholecountry</i>	0.56		0.60	0.65		1.00

N=7,741 ; Model also includes country fixed-effects

Credible interval defined by the highest posterior density method

Table 8: Country-specific effects of web-based survey mode on WTP to avoid power outages (EUR)

Variable	95% credible interval lower bound	Mean	95% credible interval upper bound	p>0
<i>France</i>	-0.24	0.04	0.31	0.60
<i>Germany</i>	-0.99	-0.76	-0.52	0.00
<i>Italy</i>	-1.32	-1.07	-0.82	0.00
<i>UK</i>	-0.60	-0.40	-0.20	0.00
<i>Austria</i>	-0.91	-0.66	-0.43	0.00
<i>Belgium</i>	-0.58	-0.30	-0.04	0.01
<i>Denmark</i>	-1.80	-1.47	-1.15	0.00
<i>Finland</i>	-1.60	-1.35	-1.10	0.00
<i>Netherlands</i>	-0.64	-0.41	-0.17	0.00
<i>Spain</i>	-1.00	-0.77	-0.53	0.00
<i>Sweden</i>	-0.97	-0.74	-0.50	0.00
<i>Portugal</i>	-0.90	-0.68	-0.47	0.00
<i>Ireland</i>	-0.95	-0.73	-0.52	0.00
<i>Luxembourg</i>	-2.22	-1.87	-1.52	0.00
<i>Bulgaria</i>	-0.74	-0.49	-0.26	0.00
<i>Czech Republic</i>	-1.22	-0.90	-0.61	0.00
<i>Estonia</i>	-1.25	-0.98	-0.72	0.00
<i>Hungary</i>	-0.67	-0.48	-0.30	0.00
<i>Latvia</i>	-0.58	-0.36	-0.15	0.00
<i>Lithuania</i>	-0.62	-0.43	-0.24	0.00
<i>Poland</i>	-1.28	-1.05	-0.83	0.00
<i>Romania</i>	-0.64	-0.41	-0.17	0.00
<i>Slovakia</i>	-0.86	-0.63	-0.41	0.00
<i>Slovenia</i>	-1.46	-1.22	-0.97	0.00
<i>Greece</i>	-0.82	-0.59	-0.36	0.00
<i>Cyprus</i>	-1.98	-1.57	-1.20	0.00
<i>Malta</i>	-0.70	-0.44	-0.18	0.00

N=7,741 ; Model also includes country fixed-effects and respondent specific variables (excluding *web*) shown in table 7; Variables are constructed as country indicators multiplied by *web*

Credible interval defined by the highest posterior density method;

3.2 Social Acceptance Model

The dependent variable for the social acceptance model is the ordinal response given by the respondent to the question regarding a new transmission line in their area: “How do you think YOU would react to the announcement of this power infrastructure program?” Respondents chose one of four possible responses ranging from DNA (definitely **not** accept) to DYA (definitely accept), and DNA responses were coded as 1 so that higher values of the dependent variable reflect higher levels of acceptance. This ordinal response structure lends itself to econometric modeling using an ordered probit approach. Further details on the ordered probit model can be found in Appendix 1.2. Respondents were also able to respond “don’t know” to this question, a response observed in 4% of the raw survey sample who were dropped in the initial data cleaning steps.

We estimate two ordered probit models for this analysis, which are distinguished by the included survey-mode variables. Both models contain country-level fixed effects variables to control for unobserved heterogeneity and a suite of respondent-specific control variables. Included variables are defined in table 5. Since we include *income* directly in this model, we lose 82 respondents due to improperly entered income information, leaving a final sample size of 7,659.

The first ordered probit model accounts for survey mode using only the *web* variable. The marginal effect of the *web* variable in this case shows the expected change in the predicted probability that the respondent gives a

DNA response when the respondent took the web-based survey as opposed to the telephone survey. The results from this model are shown in table 9. The results show that, on average, taking the web-based survey may lead to a more accepting response to the hypothetical new transmission line. This result is not statistically significant at the 5% level, but would be at the 10% level. Using the internet survey medium is estimated to decrease the probability that a respondent chooses DNA by 1.9%. While our results show that survey medium may drive responses, the effect of survey mode on response probability is of low magnitude, and is on the border of statistical significance. In comparison, changing the question preface script, by stipulating economic or environmental benefits from the transmission line, has a much larger effect, decreasing the probability of a DNA response by 10.2% and 10.5%, respectively.

We use the second ordered probit model to dig deeper into the effect of survey mode across nations. We estimate the model with the interactions between the *web* survey mode indicator and all 27 country indicators as explanatory variables. This allows us to estimate the effect of survey mode at a country-specific level. The results of the survey mode variables in this model are shown in table 10, given as the marginal effect of web-based survey mode on the predicted probability of each response category. The results show that the positive overall effect of internet survey medium on acceptance is largely driven by the responses in two nations, Greece and Cyprus. In these two nations we estimate that web surveys decreases the probability

Table 9: Social acceptance probit model results for respondent-specific variables

Variable	Coeff	Std. Err.	Marg. Eff. [†] prob(DNA)	Std. Err. prob(DNA)
<i>web</i>	0.0573	(0.0298)	-0.0197	(0.0102)
<i>T1</i>	0.296**	(0.0341)	-0.102**	(0.0116)
<i>T2</i>	0.305**	(0.0346)	-0.105**	(0.0118)
<i>T3</i>	0.0902**	(0.0340)	-0.0310**	(0.0117)
<i>income</i>	-0.00420**	(0.00150)	0.00144**	(0.000515)
<i>urban</i>	0.0458	(0.0287)	-0.0157	(0.00985)
<i>male</i>	0.218**	(0.0255)	-0.0751**	(0.00867)
<i>age35t45</i>	-0.119**	(0.0350)	0.0409**	(0.0120)
<i>age46t60</i>	-0.174**	(0.0379)	0.0598**	(0.0130)
<i>over60</i>	-0.147**	(0.0475)	0.0505**	(0.0163)
<i>hhsiz</i>	-0.0119	(0.0116)	0.00409	(0.00398)
<i>college</i>	-0.0587*	(0.0275)	0.0202*	(0.00944)
<i>posutil</i>	0.0644*	(0.0262)	-0.0221*	(0.00901)
<i>negutil</i>	-0.182**	(0.0597)	0.0626**	(0.0205)
<i>supsecsatis</i>	0.0779	(0.0474)	-0.0268	(0.0163)
<i>yearsinhome</i>	-0.00153	(0.00104)	0.000524	(0.000357)
<i>needgrids</i>	0.260**	(0.0263)	-0.0895**	(0.00893)

N=7,659 ; model also includes country fixed-effects; variables are defined in table 5; * denotes statistical significance at 5% level and ** at 1% level.

[†] Marginal effect of a one unit increase in variable on probability respondent gives a DNA (definitely not accept) response

of a DNA response by 13.4% and 14.9%, respectively, which is even larger than the effect of adding ancillary benefits of the transmission line to the preface script. In other nations the marginal effect of survey mode is not statistically significant, except for Lithuania, which exhibits a different result where the web survey medium is associated with decreased acceptance levels and increased probability of a DNA response. Thus, the overall positive effect of web surveys on acceptance is mostly driven by the strong effect of this survey mode exhibited in Greece and Cyprus, whereas the survey mode is not affecting responses to the acceptance question to a statistically significant degree in 24 of the 27 sample nations.

Table 10: Country-specific marginal effects of web-based survey mode on the probability of choosing a given response category

Variable	P(DNA)		P(PNA)		P(PYA)		P(DYA)	
	Marg. Eff.	Std. Err.						
<i>France</i>	-0.0489	(0.0423)	-0.00318	(0.00278)	0.0252	(0.0219)	0.0268	(0.0232)
<i>Germany</i>	-0.0681	(0.0424)	-0.00443	(0.00279)	0.0351	(0.0219)	0.0374	(0.0232)
<i>Italy</i>	-0.0135	(0.0448)	-0.000875	(0.00291)	0.00694	(0.0231)	0.00739	(0.0246)
<i>UK</i>	-0.0581	(0.0434)	-0.00378	(0.00284)	0.0300	(0.0224)	0.0319	(0.0238)
<i>Austria</i>	-0.0445	(0.0437)	-0.00289	(0.00286)	0.0230	(0.0225)	0.0244	(0.0240)
<i>Belgium</i>	-0.00539	(0.0434)	-0.000350	(0.00282)	0.00278	(0.0224)	0.00296	(0.0238)
<i>Denmark</i>	-0.0385	(0.0466)	-0.00250	(0.00304)	0.0198	(0.0241)	0.0211	(0.0256)
<i>Finland</i>	-0.0104	(0.0366)	-0.000676	(0.00238)	0.00537	(0.0189)	0.00571	(0.0201)
<i>Netherlands</i>	-0.0440	(0.0453)	-0.00286	(0.00295)	0.0227	(0.0234)	0.0242	(0.0249)
<i>Spain</i>	-0.00943	(0.0420)	-0.000613	(0.00273)	0.00487	(0.0217)	0.00518	(0.0230)
<i>Sweden</i>	-0.0222	(0.0400)	-0.00144	(0.00260)	0.0115	(0.0207)	0.0122	(0.0220)
<i>Portugal</i>	-0.0300	(0.0482)	-0.00195	(0.00313)	0.0155	(0.0249)	0.0165	(0.0265)
<i>Ireland</i>	-0.0610	(0.0461)	-0.00397	(0.00303)	0.0315	(0.0238)	0.0335	(0.0253)
<i>Luxembourg</i>	0.00184	(0.0417)	0.000119	(0.00271)	-0.000948	(0.0215)	-0.00101	(0.0229)
<i>Bulgaria</i>	0.0150	(0.0434)	0.000972	(0.00283)	-0.00771	(0.0224)	-0.00821	(0.0238)
<i>Czech Republic</i>	0.0218	(0.0428)	0.00142	(0.00280)	-0.0113	(0.0221)	-0.0120	(0.0235)
<i>Estonia</i>	0.0306	(0.0460)	0.00199	(0.00300)	-0.0158	(0.0237)	-0.0168	(0.0253)
<i>Hungary</i>	-0.0512	(0.0394)	-0.00333	(0.00258)	0.0264	(0.0203)	0.0281	(0.0216)
<i>Latvia</i>	0.0100	(0.0466)	0.000651	(0.00303)	-0.00517	(0.0241)	-0.00550	(0.0256)
<i>Lithuania</i>	0.0972*	(0.0441)	0.00632*	(0.00300)	-0.0502*	(0.0227)	-0.0534*	(0.0243)
<i>Poland</i>	-0.0451	(0.0394)	-0.00293	(0.00257)	0.0233	(0.0203)	0.0248	(0.0216)
<i>Romania</i>	0.0521	(0.0475)	0.00339	(0.00312)	-0.0269	(0.0245)	-0.0286	(0.0261)
<i>Slovakia</i>	0.0663	(0.0471)	0.00431	(0.00313)	-0.0342	(0.0242)	-0.0364	(0.0259)
<i>Greece</i>	-0.134**	(0.0457)	-0.00872**	(0.00317)	0.0692**	(0.0236)	0.0737**	(0.0251)
<i>Cyprus</i>	-0.149*	(0.0587)	-0.00970*	(0.00401)	0.0769*	(0.0303)	0.0819*	(0.0323)
<i>Slovenia</i>	-0.0491	(0.0477)	-0.00319	(0.00311)	0.0253	(0.0246)	0.0270	(0.0262)
<i>Malta</i>	0.0213	(0.0531)	0.00138	(0.00346)	-0.0110	(0.0274)	-0.0117	(0.0291)

N=7,659 ; Model also includes country fixed-effects and respondent specific variables (excluding *web*) shown in table 9; * denotes statistical significance at 5% level and ** at 1% level.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

In the context of a choice experiment assessing WTP to avoid power outages we find clear results that internet survey respondents state lower WTP than their phone-surveyed counterparts. Strikingly, this result holds over 26 of the 27 nations in the sample, suggesting that choice experiments in this context will be affected by survey-mode-related bias regardless of the nation where the study is applied. However, our results show that the magnitude of survey-mode bias can, and likely will, vary across nations. European nations, despite their geographic proximity, are highly heterogeneous in terms of their historical, cultural and institutional backgrounds. All of these factors, along with sampling effects, likely play a role in driving the magnitude of the observed survey-mode bias across nations, which makes unraveling the causes of this heterogeneity difficult. However, this does not rule out the possibility that more homogenous, but distinct regions, such as U.S. states, could also have varying responses to survey-mode. Such a dynamic would explain some of the conflicting findings of earlier literature (e.g. Whittaker et al. (1998) vs. Loomis and King (1994)).

In the research context of social acceptance to energy infrastructure we find a different result. While the overall effect of internet survey mode suggests this mode may increase stated acceptance, the magnitude of this effect is small, and the coefficient is only significant at the 10% level. Looking at the country-specific effects, we find that two nations are mainly driving this

result, Greece and Cyprus, where the effect of survey-mode is having a strong impact on responses to the acceptance question. The survey mode does not show a statistically significant effect in the other 24 nations. It is interesting to note that Greece and Cyprus share a language, and to some extent have similar culture and history, which could possibly account for their similarity in our findings.

Comparing the results with respect to survey mode across contexts we find evidence that survey mode effects can vary based on the research question posed. Even though both of our research contexts deal broadly with energy, and both questions were included in the same survey, responses to the questions were not equally affected by survey mode. Specifically, the responses to the choice experiment eliciting WTP to avoid power outages showed much stronger and more consistent survey-mode effects than the responses to the social acceptance of energy infrastructure question.

To attempt to understand why survey-mode effects may differ across research contexts we consider how the different types of survey-induced biases may vary across contexts. We note the conceptual findings in section 1.1 and specifically Proposition 1.3, which shows the effects of a situation where sampling biases and measurement biases are both present. The high likelihood of sampling biases in between the web and phone based samples in this study are noted in section 2 and shown by sample statistics such as response rates and socio-demographic composition of the samples. This is due to the different sampling frames from the internet and phone respondents,

and different propensities for non-response and avidity bias since the web participants were incentivized slightly for their cooperation. However, these sampling bias effects are expected to be present in both research contexts, as the same individuals responded to both experimental scenarios. Nevertheless we see one research context strongly affected by survey mode and the other context generally unaffected by survey mode. This may imply that the remaining bias type, measurement bias, may be varying across research contexts. This supposition is upheld by the recent work of Boyle et al. (2016) who took great care to control for sampling biases, but still find significant differences between values elicited via web and mail surveys.

Given the contexts under study, we suggest a social desirability effect is a likely candidate to be driving the disparity in measurement bias across research contexts. With social desirability bias the respondent wants to give the socially appropriate answer to the survey question when on the phone, or present, with a survey administrator. In the context of power outages, we would argue that the socially appropriate behavior is clear. Since power outages have a negative impact on the majority of people affected, and can even be dangerous if crucial systems go down, when given an opportunity to avoid this bad outcome by paying a small fee, the socially responsible thing to do is to pay the fee. Phone survey respondents may feel this social pressure more acutely due to the presence of an interviewer on the other end of the line, and thus are more likely to accept the bid price. This dynamic would explain our survey mode results in the context of the choice experiment.

Conversely, in the context of social acceptance of energy infrastructure we argue that the socially appropriate response is not clear. On one hand, the NIMBY response is often stigmatized as hypocritical (Meyer, 2010) such that a phone respondent may feel more social pressure to accept the nearby infrastructure, which is consistent with the result we see in Cyprus and Greece. On the other hand, defending one's locale from the perceived detriments of a new transmission line may be viewed as the appropriate response (Oreskes, 2014). This sentiment is evidenced by the numerous local organizations that have sprung up to fight against energy infrastructure projects across Europe. A respondent of this mindset may feel social pressure to oppose the infrastructure project when on the phone with an interviewer, which would lead to the response bias exhibited by Lithuanian participants in table 10.

In summation, our results show strong differences in the magnitude of survey mode bias across research contexts. This suggests that the inconsistent findings of past literature with respect to survey mode effects may be due to the varying contexts and geographies under which these studies were performed. Researchers should think critically about their specific research context and the potential causes of measurement bias within this context when selecting a survey medium. While bias in survey responses remains a critical issue moving forward for the applied social science community, this paper has taken the critical step in illuminating the heterogeneous effects of survey mode across geographies and research contexts. Further research is needed in this area to unveil the optimal survey strategy for specific contexts

and geographies.

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1 Appendix

1.1 Additional econometric details for WTP model

We specify each respondent i 's indirect utility¹¹ representation for two cases for each outage scenario $s \in \{1 \dots S\}$: in the event of a power outage with the characteristics stipulated by s denoted as \tilde{v}_{is}^* , and in the event that they

¹¹Indirect utility is the level of well-being for a given individual after she has optimized over the consumption of all other goods and services.

pay to avoid such an outage denoted as \tilde{v}_{is} .

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{v}_{is}^* &= \gamma_i m_i - d_s \mathbf{x}'_{is} \boldsymbol{\beta}^* + d_s \tilde{\epsilon}_{is} \\ \tilde{v}_{is} &= \gamma_i (m_i - P_{is}) + d_s \tilde{\epsilon}_{i0}\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

Where m_i is the household income of respondent i , P_{is} is the bid price entered as a positive number, \mathbf{x}'_{is} are observed respondent and scenario characteristics, and d_s is the outage duration measured in hours. The error terms capture scenario-specific factors that are unobserved yet affect utility. The error terms are scaled by the duration of the outage d_s , to account for the larger variance in indirect utility associated with longer outages. Lengthy outages expose individuals to a wider variety of potential nuisances with greater extremes. For instance, a short outage may ruin a meal in the midst of being cooked, while a longer outage could ruin a series of meals that would have been cooked *and* spoil the entire freezer full of food. We can show the model in “utility-space” by subtracting the above two utilities.

$$v_{is}^* = \tilde{v}_{is} - \tilde{v}_{is}^* = d_s \mathbf{x}'_{is} \boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \gamma_i P_{is} + d_s (\tilde{\epsilon}_{i0} - \tilde{\epsilon}_{is})\tag{5}$$

We elect to estimate this model in “surplus” space for ease of interpretation and improved credibility of the results, as shown, among others, by Train and Weeks (2005) and Sonnier et al. (2007). Thus, we divide through the previous equation by the marginal utility of income γ_i . This yields v_{is} which can be interpreted as the difference between the full WTP to avoid the outage

in menu s and P_{is} . The model is then written as:

$$v_{is} = \frac{v_{is}^*}{\gamma_i} = d_s \mathbf{x}'_{is} \boldsymbol{\beta} - P_{is} + d_s \kappa_{is},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{is} &= \frac{\boldsymbol{\beta}^*}{\gamma_i}, \\ \kappa_{is} &= \frac{(\tilde{\epsilon}_{i0} - \tilde{\epsilon}_{is})}{\gamma_i} \quad \text{where} \quad \kappa_{is} = \alpha_i + \epsilon_{is}, \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

with

$$\alpha_i \sim N(0, \delta_\alpha^2), \quad \epsilon_{is} \sim N(0, \delta_{i,\epsilon}^2),$$

where we split the error term into within-respondent and between-respondent segments, so we can estimate the random effect term α_i for each respondent. For a vector of observed binary choice responses, \mathbf{y}_i , where a 1 denotes that the respondent accepted the bid price and a 0 denotes rejection of the bid price, a response of 1 will be observed when $v_{is} > 0$. The hierarchical structure of the model suggests a Bayesian approach, in which the conditional likelihood $p(y_{is} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \delta_\alpha^2, \delta_{i,\epsilon}^2)$ is combined with the distribution of the variances within respondents, $p(\delta_{i,\epsilon}^2 | w)$, and with the distributions of the common parameters $p(\delta_\alpha^2 | \mathbf{h})$ and $p(\boldsymbol{\beta} | \mathbf{g})$. We select an inverted Gamma distribution for $\delta_{i,\epsilon}^2$, which is considered as a first-stage prior in a Bayesian setting, such that $\delta_{i,\epsilon}^2 \sim IG(r, \varrho)$. r is chosen as fixed parameter, such that ϱ remains as unknown hyperparameter and follows a second-stage prior distribution $p(\varrho | \mathbf{q})$.

The joint posterior distribution is then given by

$$p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \delta_\alpha^2, \delta_{1,\epsilon}^2, \dots, \delta_{N,\epsilon}^2, \varrho | \mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_N, \mathbf{g}, \mathbf{h}, r, \mathbf{q}) \propto \prod_i p(\mathbf{y}_{is} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \delta_\alpha^2, \delta_{i,\epsilon}^2) p(\boldsymbol{\beta} | \mathbf{g}) p(\delta_\alpha^2 | \mathbf{h}) p(\delta_{i,\epsilon}^2 | r, \varrho) p(\varrho | \mathbf{q}) \quad (7)$$

We select a Gamma distribution as prior of ϱ , giving

$$\varrho \sim G(a_\varrho, A_\varrho), \quad (8)$$

and likewise select a inverted Gamma distribution as prior of the variance between respondents, such that

$$\delta_\alpha^2 \sim IG(a_{\delta_\alpha^2}, A_{\delta_\alpha^2}). \quad (9)$$

For the common parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ we define a normal prior,

$$\boldsymbol{\beta} \sim N(\mathbf{a}_\beta, \mathbf{A}_\beta). \quad (10)$$

The resulting full conditional posterior distributions are standard in Bayesian econometric literature and we refer the reader to Rossi et al. (2005) for details. We draw from the posterior via a Gibbs Sampler. The final model output is 20,000 draws of each estimable parameter, with 10,000 of these draws as burn-in. Using these parameter draws we then calculate the mean

WTP in table 6 to avoid an hour of power outage for each respondent-scenario observation as $v_{is} + P_{is} = d_s \mathbf{x}'_{is} \boldsymbol{\beta} + d_s(\alpha_i + \epsilon_{is})$, and setting $d_s = 1$ to denote an hour of power outage. The stochastic term ϵ_{is} is assumed to have a mean of zero and so is in practice omitted from the calculation while the draws of the random effect term α_i are used following Campbell (2007). This is an in-sample calculation which loops over all 10,000 usable draws of each parameter and all 61,928 observations (7,741 respondents with 8 choices per respondent). This results in 10,000 draws from an empirical distribution of WTP for each observation. These draws are summarized by country to yield the results in Table 6.

1.2 Additional econometric details for the Ordered Probit model

The ordered probit is a standard modeling approach for ordinal data that leads to intuitive and easily interpretable results. The ordered probit model, as specified in equation 11, is motivated by a continuous, unobserved latent variable y_i^* that exists for each individual i . In this case it is useful to think of y_i^* as respondent i 's perceived change in indirect utility due to the development. The respondent then selects DYA and PYA, for higher values of y_i^* , and PNA or DNA for lower values of y_i^* . Survey answers are the *observed response*, which we denote as y_i . The latent variable y_i^* maps the observed response, such that if y_i^* falls between two thresholds y_i takes a

certain value. This is shown in equation 11.

$$\begin{aligned}
y_i^* &= \mathbf{X}_i\boldsymbol{\beta} + \epsilon_i \quad \epsilon \sim N(0, 1) \\
y_i &= 1(\text{DNA}) \quad \text{iff} \quad y_i^* \leq v_1 \\
y_i &= 2(\text{PNA}) \quad \text{iff} \quad v_1 < y_i^* \leq v_2 \\
y_i &= 3(\text{PYA}) \quad \text{iff} \quad v_2 < y_i^* \leq v_3 \\
y_i &= 4(\text{DYA}) \quad \text{iff} \quad y_i^* \geq v_3,
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is a vector of slope coefficients for the explanatory variables included in \mathbf{X}_i , and v_1 , v_2 and v_3 are threshold values that are estimated along with $\boldsymbol{\beta}$. The $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ coefficient estimates are transformed into marginal effects which relate the change in the predicted probability that the survey response (y) falls within a given category due to a change in explanatory variables. These marginal effects are calculated as the averages response, meaning that the change in the predicted probability of a given response for a one unit change in a single variable is calculated many times, with all other variables set to all combinations of observed values. This effect is then averaged over all of these calculations to obtain the average response of the predicted probability.